

CODEN [USA] : IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at : <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF IMMEDIATE RELEASE TABLETS OF CAPECITABINE

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In the present research work Capecitabine immediate release tablets were prepared by direct compression method using varying concentrations of Crospovidone, Cros carmellose sodium and Sodium starch glycolate .The formulations prepared were evaluated for pre compression and post compression parameters. From the drug excipient compatibility studies, we observe that there are no interactions between the pure drug Capecitabine and optimized formulation which indicates there are no physical changes. Post compression parameters was found to be within limits. Among all the formulation prepared the tablet containing 60mg of CCS shows 99.10 % of the drug release within 45mints.

Keywords: *Capecitabine, Crospovidone, Cros carmellose sodium and Sodium starch glycolate*

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Please cite this article in press **Anitha peta et al., Formulation And Evaluation Of Immediate Release Tablets Of Capecitabine., Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2024; 11 (09).**

INTRODUCTION:

The Oral route is one of the most sought after route for the systemic effect due to its ease of ingestion, simple, safest, convenient, non-invasive, versatility and most importantly, patient compliance. Solid oral delivery systems are cheaply manufactured because they don't require sterile conditions.¹ Although, increased focus and interest generated in the area of controlled release and targeted drug delivery system in recent years, tablet dosage forms that are intended to be swallowed whole, disintegrate, and release their medicaments fast and furiously in the gastrointestinal tract.²

An ideal dosage regimen of drug therapy is the one, which immediately nab the desired therapeutic concentration of drug in plasma (or at the site of action) and maintains it constantly for the entire duration treatment.³ Of late, the scientists have focused their attention on the formulation immediately released tablet. The effort of developing a rapidly disintegrating tablet is accomplished by using suitable diluents and super disintegrants.⁴ Definition: Immediate Release Tablets: Immediate release tablets are invented to disintegrate and release their dosage form with no special rate controlling features, such as special coatings and other techniques. Immediate release tablets are those which disintegrate swiftly and get dissolved to release the medicaments.⁵ The oral bioavailability of drug dependent on disintegration, dissolution and various physiological factors.⁶ An immediate release dosage form helps a manufacturer to diversify market and simultaneously offering patients a convenient dosage form or dosage regimen.⁷ Several technologies are available to manufacture immediate-release tablets.⁸⁻⁹ The most common preparation methods are molding, lyophilization or freeze drying, direct compression, spray drying and sublimation.¹⁰⁻¹²

The main aim of the present study is to formulation and *In vitro* evaluation of Capecitabine Immediate release tablets.

MATERIALS

Table 1: List of materials used

Name of the material	Source
Capecitabine	Procured From Hetero labs Hyderabad, India Provided by SURA LABS, Dilsukhnagar, Hyderabad.
Crospovidone	S.D. Fine Chemicals. Pvt Ltd, Mumbai, India

Cros carmellose sodium	S.D. Fine Chemicals. Pvt Ltd
Sodium starch glycolate	S.D. Fine Chemicals. Pvt Ltd

METHODOLOGY

Buffer Preparation:

Preparation of 0.2M Potassium dihydrogen orthophosphate solution: Accurately weighed 27.218 gm of monobasic potassium dihydrogen orthophosphate was dissolved in 1000mL of distilled water and mixed.

Preparation of 0.2M sodium hydroxide solution: Accurately weighed 8 gm sodium hydroxide pellets were dissolved 1000ml of distilled water and mixed.

Preparation of pH 6.8 Phosphate buffer: Accurately measured 250ml of 0.2M potassium Dihydrogen orthophosphate and 112.5 ml 0.2M NaOH was taken into the 1000ml volumetric flask. Volume was made up to 1000ml with distilled water.

Pre formulation Studies

Pre formulation involves the application of biopharmaceutical principles to the physicochemical parameters of drug substance are characterized with the goal of designing optimum drug delivery system.

Analytical method development for Capecitabine:

a) Determination of absorption maxima

A spectrum of the working standards was obtained by scanning from 200-400nm against the reagent blank to fix absorption maxima. The λ_{max} was found to be 240nm. Hence all further investigation was carried out at the same wavelength.

b) Preparation of Standard graph in pH 6.8 phosphate buffer

100 mg of Capecitabine was dissolved in 100 mL of pH 6.8 phosphate buffer to give a concentration in 1mg/mL (1000 μ g/mL) 1 ml was taken and diluted to 100 ml with pH 6.8 phosphate buffer to give a concentration of 0.01 mg/ml (10 μ g/ml). From this stock solution aliquots of 1 ml, 2ml, 3ml, 4ml, 5ml, were pipette out in 10 ml volumetric flask and volume was made up to the mark with pH 6.8 phosphate buffer to produce concentration of 10, 20, 30, 40 and 50 μ g/ml respectively. The absorbance of each concentration was measured at respective (λ_{max}) i.e., 240nm.

Formulation Development:

- Drug and different concentrations for super Disintegrates and required ingredients were accurately weighed and passed through a 40-mesh screen to get uniform size particles and mixed in a glass mortar for 15 minutes.
- The obtained blend was lubricated with Magnesium stearate and glidant (Talc)

was added and mixing was continued for further 5 minutes.

- The resultant mixture was directly compressed into tablets by using punch of

rotary tablet compression machine. Compression force was kept constant for all formulations.

Table 2: Formulation of Immediate Release tablets

INGREDIENTS	FORMULATION CODE								
	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7	C8	C9
Capecitabine	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
Crospovidone	30	60	90	-	-	-	-	-	-
Cros carmellose sodium	-	-	-	30	60	90	-	-	-
Sodium starch glycolate	-	-	-	-	-	-	30	60	90
MCC	335	305	275	335	305	275	335	305	275
Aspartame	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15
Mg stearate	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
Talc	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
Total Weight of Tablet (mg)	500	500	500	500	500	500	500	500	500

Total weight of tablets = 500mg

Evaluation parameters:

Pre compression parameters:

Measurement of Micromeritic Properties of Powders

1. Angle of repose

The angle of repose of API powder is determined by the funnel method. The accurately weight powder blend are taken in the funnel. The height of the funnel is adjusted in way that, the tip of the funnel just touched the apex of the powder blend. The powder blend is allowed to flow through the funnel freely on the surface. The diameter of the powder cone is measured and angle of repose is calculated using the following equation.

$$\tan \theta = h/r \quad \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

where, h and r are the height and radius of the powder cone.

2. Bulk density

The powder sample under test is screened through sieve No.18 and the sample equivalent to 25 gm is weighed and filled in a 100 ml graduated cylinder and the powder is leveled and the unsettled volume, V_0 is noted. The bulk density is calculated in g/cm^3 by the formula.

$$\text{Bulk density} = M/V_0 \quad \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

M= Powder mass

V_0 = apparent unstirred volume

3. Tapped density

The powder sample under test is screened through sieve No.18 and the weight of the sample equivalent to 25 gm filled in 100 ml granulated cylinder. The mechanical tapping of cylinder is carried out using tapped density tester at a nominal rate for 500 times initially and the tapped volume V_f is noted. Tappings

are proceeded further for an additional tapping 750 times and tapped volume, V_b is noted. The difference between two tapping volume is less than 2%, V_b is considered as a tapped volume V_f . the tapped density is calculated in g/cm^3 by the formula.

$$\text{Tapped density} = M/V_f \quad \dots\dots\dots(3)$$

M= weight of sample powder taken

V_f = Tapped volume

4. Compressibility Index

The Compressibility Index of the powder blend is determined by Carr's compressibility index to know the flow character of a powder. The formula for Carr's Index is an below:

$$\text{Carr's Index (\%)} = [(TD-BD)/TD] \times 100 \quad \dots\dots\dots(4)$$

5. Hauser's ratio

The Hauser's ratio is a number that is correlated to the flowability of a powder or granular material. The ratio of tapped density to bulk density of the powders is called the Hauser's ratio. It is calculated by the following equation.

$$H = \rho_T / \rho_B \quad \dots\dots\dots(5)$$

Where ρ_T = tapped density, ρ_B = bulk density

Post compression parameters:

a) Thickness

The thickness of tablets was determined by using Digital micrometer. Ten individual tablets from each batch were used and the results averaged.

b) Weight variation

Twenty tablets randomly selected from each batch and individually weighed. The average weight and standard deviation three batches were calculated. It passes the test weight variation test if not more than

two of the individual tablets weights deviate from the average weight by more than the allowed percentage deviation and more deviate by more than twice the percentage shown. It was calculated on an electronic weighing balance.

c) Friability

The friability values of the tablets were determined using a Roche-type friabilator. Accurately weighed six tablets were placed in Roche friabilator and rotated at 25rpm for 4 min.

Percentage friability was calculated using the following equation.

$$\text{Friability} = \left(\frac{w_0 - w}{w_0} \right) \times 100$$

d) Assay

The content of drug was carried out by five randomly selected tablets of each formulation. The five tablets were grinded in mortar to get powder; this powder was dissolved in pH 6.8 phosphate buffer by sonication for 30 min and filtered through filter paper. The drug content was analyzed spectrophotometrically at 240nm using UV spectrophotometer. Each measurement was carried out in triplicate and the average drug content was calculated.

e) Disintegration test

Six tablets were taken randomly from each batch and placed in USP disintegration apparatus baskets. Apparatus was run for 10 minutes and the basket was lift from the fluid, observe whether all of the tablets have disintegrated.

f) Dissolution test of Capecitabine tablets

Drug release from Capecitabine tablets was determined by using dissolution test United States Pharmacopoeia (USP) 24 type II (paddle). The

parameters used for performing the dissolution were pH 6.8 Phosphate Buffer as the dissolution medium of quantity 500ml. the whole study is being carried out at a temperature of 37°C and at speed of 50 rpm.

5 ml aliquots of dissolution media were withdrawn each time at suitable time intervals (5, 10, 15, 20, 30 and 45 minutes) and replaced with fresh medium. After withdrawing, samples were filtered and analyzed after appropriate dilution by UV Spectrophotometer. The concentration was calculated using standard calibration curve.

Drug-Excipients compatibility studies:

Drug Excipients compatibility studies were carried out by mixing the drug with various excipients in different proportions (In 1:1 ratio were prepared to have maximum likelihood interaction between them) was placed in a vial, and closed with rubber stopper and sealed properly.

The main aim of the present study is to formulation and *In vitro* evaluation of Capecitabine Immediate release tablets.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Determination of $\lambda_{\max}$:

The prepared stock solution was scanned between 200-400 nm to determine the absorption maxima. It was found to be 240nm.

Calibration curve of Capecitabine

The standard curve of Capecitabine was obtained and good correlation was obtained with R² value of 0.9999 the medium selected was pH 6.8 phosphate buffer.

Table 3: Standard graph values of Capecitabine at 280nm in pH 6.8 phosphate buffer

Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance
0	0
10	0.117
20	0.246
30	0.368
40	0.488
50	0.608

Fig 1: Standard curve of Capecitabine

Evaluation:

Characterization of precompression blend:

The precompression blend of Capecitabine was characterized with respect to angle of repose, bulk density, tapped density, Carr's index and Hausner's ratio. Angle of repose was less than 29.9° , Carr's index values were less than 27.75 for the precompression blend of all the batches indicating good to fair flowability and compressibility. Hausner's ratio was less than 1.43 for all batches indicating good flow properties.

Table 4: Physical properties of precompression blend

Formulation code	Angle of repose (Θ)	Bulk density (gm/cm^3)	Tapped density (gm/cm^3)	Carr's index (%)	Hausner's ratio
C1	$32^\circ 47' \pm 0.62$	0.25 ± 0.01	0.27 ± 0.01	10.41 ± 0.27	1.08 ± 0.03
C2	$33^\circ 28' \pm 0.83$	0.28 ± 0.01	0.31 ± 0.05	11.55 ± 3.52	1.13 ± 0.04
C3	$33^\circ 21' \pm 0.83$	0.24 ± 0.03	0.27 ± 0.03	11.22 ± 4.21	1.12 ± 0.05
C4	$32^\circ 29' \pm 0.91$	0.29 ± 0.01	0.33 ± 0.01	7.09 ± 2.82	1.13 ± 0.03
C5	$34^\circ 17' \pm 1.07$	0.23 ± 0.01	0.28 ± 0.01	13.10 ± 1.14	1.20 ± 0.04
C6	$34^\circ 06' \pm 0.53$	0.27 ± 0.06	0.31 ± 0.07	17.04 ± 2.82	1.13 ± 0.03
C7	$31^\circ 09' \pm 2.12$	0.26 ± 0.03	0.29 ± 0.02	11.83 ± 2.85	1.11 ± 0.05
C8	$30^\circ 01' \pm 1.37$	0.25 ± 0.02	0.29 ± 0.04	10.44 ± 3.94	1.15 ± 0.07
C9	$33^\circ 01' \pm 1.18$	0.22 ± 0.02	0.25 ± 0.25	13.32 ± 5.22	1.15 ± 0.15

All the values represent $n=3$

Evaluation of tablets:

Physical evaluation of Capecitabine Immediate release tablets:

The results of the weight variation, Hardness, Thickness, Friability, and Drug content of tablets are given in table 8.3. All the tablets of different batches complied with the official requirement of weight variation as their weight variation passes the limit. The hardness of the tablets ranged from $4.39 - 4.61 \text{ kg/cm}^2$ and the friability values were $< 0.69\%$ indicating that the tablets were compact and hard. The thickness of the tablets ranged from $2.63 - 2.85$. All the formulations satisfied the content of the drug as they contained $97.42 - 99.35\%$ of Capecitabine and good uniformity in drug content was observed. Thus all physical attributes of the prepared tablets were found to be practically within control limits.

Table 5: Evaluation of Capecitabine Immediate release tablets

Formulation code	Weight variation (mg)	Thickness (mm)	Hardness (Kg/cm ²)	Friability (%)	Content uniformity (%)	In Vitro Disintegration time (seconds)
C1	498.31	2.85	4.38	0.27	98.61	15
C2	495.22	2.75	4.56	0.34	99.32	22
C3	499.48	2.77	4.62	0.42	97.42	18
C4	492.37	2.81	4.35	0.39	98.82	23
C5	500.62	2.63	4.53	0.21	99.35	21
C6	501.78	2.83	4.61	0.49	97.64	19
C7	496.85	2.72	4.39	0.55	98.22	36
C8	499.32	2.76	4.48	0.36	98.11	23
C9	505.22	2.83	4.57	0.42	99.31	28

Fig 2: In vitro disintegration time graph

In vitro Dissolution: The drug release rate from tablets was studied using the USP type II dissolution test apparatus. The dissolution medium was 500 ml of pH 6.8 phosphate buffer at 50 rpm at a temperature of 37 ± 0.5 °C. Samples of 5 ml were collected at different time intervals up to 30min and has analyzed after appropriate dilution by using UV spectrophotometer at 240nm

Table 6: *In vitro* data for formulation C1- C9

TIME (Minutes)	IN VITRO DRUG RELEASE								
	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7	C8	C9
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5	52.42	57.99	58.71	60.20	63.96	55.75	64.14	67.73	61.58
10	60.95	60.57	62.96	73.71	77.14	62.18	72.61	79.92	65.74
15	67.15	65.52	70.35	76.17	80.27	70.62	76.39	82.70	74.93
20	76.50	71.78	78.82	89.92	90.58	86.10	82.27	87.21	86.46
30	81.89	76.44	85.96	90.80	92.16	87.73	87.98	91.64	90.33
45	86.32	89.12	91.28	95.42	99.10	93.14	92.71	95.83	94.92

Fig 4: *In vitro* dissolution data for formulations C4-C6

Fig 5: In vitro dissolution data for formulations C7-C9

Formulations prepared with Crospovidone showed maximum drug release i.e., 91.28% (C3 formulation) at 45min in 500 mg of blend.

Formulations prepared with Cros carmellose sodium showed maximum drug release i.e., 99.10% (C5 formulation) at 45 min in 500 mg of blend.

Formulations prepared with Sodium starch glycolate showed maximum drug release i.e., 95.83% (C8 formulation) at 45 min in 500 mg of blend.

Among all formulations C5 considered as optimised formulation which showed maximum drug release at 45min i.e., 99.10 %. Finally concluded that C5 formulation contains Cros carmellose sodium was optimized formulation.

Drug-Excipient compatibility studies by FTIR studies:

Fig 6: FTIR spectra of pure drug

Fig 7: FTIR spectra of optimized formulation

Capecitabine was mixed with various proportions of excipients showed no colour change at the end of two months, providing no drug –excipient interactions.

CONCLUSION:

This study successfully indicated that immediate release tablets. Immediate release tablet is needed to give rapid action. The oral immediate release tablets of Capecitabine which disintegrates rapidly there by reducing the time of onset of pharmacological action. Crospovidone, Croscarmellose sodium and Sodium starch glycolate were used as polymers. In all the formulations. Magnesium stearate and talc were used as lubricant and glidant respectively. The results of the drug –excipient compatibility studies revealed that there was no chemical interaction between the pure drug and excipients. Direct compression method was employed to formulate the tablets because of its cost effectiveness and due to reduced number of manufacturing steps. The pre compression parameters like bulk density, tapped density, carrs index and angle of repose were determined. All the formulations showed acceptable flow properties. The post compression parameters like the hardness, thickness, friability and weight variation and In vitro release were carried out and the values were found to be within the acceptable limits. Among all the formulations C5 shows 99.10% drug release at the end of 45 mins. C5 contains Cross carmellose sodium with 60mg. It shows better % drug release. When compared to other formulations. So C5 was considered as the optimized formulation.

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